

Correctness Arguments

We will first conduct a proof for the simpler, non-restartable case, and then extend it to the restartable case. Recall that the `enter-snapshot` step is a range query's first call to `GetNextFromBundle` and that a call to `GetNextFromBundle` returns the node pointed to by the bundle entry satisfying the given timestamp.

Definition 1. A bundle entry *satisfies* a timestamp t if it is the most recent entry whose timestamp is less than or equal to t .

Definition 2. A node *exists* at time t if it is reachable by following bundle entries satisfying t from the root (i.e., using `GetNextFromBundle`).

Definition 3. The *abstract state* of a bundled data structure at time t is defined as the set of all keys that exist in the data structure at time t .

Based on Definition 3, we can prove that a range query is linearizable by showing that it observes all keys that are in the abstract state of the data structure at its linearization point of the range query, and does not observe any other keys.

We start our proof with the following two lemmas.

Lemma 1. *A bundle of a node that is in the data structure at time t has exactly one bundle entry that satisfies t .*

Proof. We assume an invariant in the data structure design that during the insertion of a new node n , each of its bundles is initialized with a pending entry that is later finalized. If the insertion is linearized at t , then the entry is finalized with t . If no further entries are added, this entry will be the one satisfying any future timestamps. If future entries are added, they will be finalized with higher unique timestamps because each update atomically fetch-and-increments the global timestamp. Because timestamps are unique, only one of them will satisfy a given timestamp greater than t . Note that memory reclamation never reclaims the most recent bundle entry or any entry satisfying the linearization point of an ongoing range query. \square

Lemma 2. *The `enter-snapshot` step of a non-restartable range query RQ returns a node that exists in the data structure at RQ 's linearization point.*

Proof. The lemma follows directly from the fact that the `enter-snapshot` step of a non-restartable range query starts from the root. At RQ 's linearization point, the root was trivially in the data structure, and thus, by Lemma 1 the root is guaranteed to have an entry that satisfies RQ 's linearization point. \square

Next we prove, in Theorem 1, that a bundled data structure with non-restartable range queries is linearizable. Briefly, Theorem 1 will formally prove that the linearization points are valid. It hinges on demonstrating that range queries (and therefore contains operations) are linearizable by showing that (1) a range query does not visit a node that does not belong to its linearizable snapshot and that (2) a range query visits all nodes belonging to its linearizable snapshot.

Theorem 1. *Bundled data structures with non-restartable range queries are linearizable.*

Proof. We leverage the (correct) observation of Reviewer 3 that the linearization point of updates is effectively Line 4 in Algorithm 1 (i.e., incrementing `globalTS`). This correctly linearizes update operations because the global timestamp is only incremented after the necessary pending bundle entries are installed, blocking conflicting update operations. Hence, the global timestamp enforces an order among conflicting update operations.

The next step is to show that range queries (with `contains` being a special case of range query) are linearized at the moment they snapshot `globalTS` (Line 3 in Algorithm 3). Consider a range query

operation RQ whose linearization point is t_{RQ} . Its first step is to perform the **enter-snapshot** step. By Lemma 2, the traversal begins at a node that was in the data structure at t_{RQ} . Because of Lemma 1, this node also has a bundle entry satisfying t_{RQ} . By induction, all nodes in the range that exist at t_{RQ} can be reached via calls to **GetNextFromBundle** that use t_{RQ} .

It remains to demonstrate how the traversal will interact with concurrent updates. To cover those cases, assume an arbitrary key k , within RQ's range. We then have the following possible executions:

1. No node with a key equal to k exists in the data structure when the range query is invoked, and either:
 - (a) No insert operation on k is executed concurrently with RQ. Thus, RQ traverses using **GetNextFromBundle** and will not visit any node with key k .
 - (b) An insert(k) operation INS is executed concurrently with RQ, for which there are two possibilities:
 - i. INS is linearized before RQ. If INS increments **globalTS** before RQ takes its snapshot of **globalTS**, it implies that INS also installed the necessary pending bundle entries before RQ reads **globalTS**. This means that RQ will block until INS finishes, and thus RQ will include k since INS finalizes the bundles with a timestamp satisfying t_{RQ} .
 - ii. INS is linearized after RQ. If INS increments **globalTS** after RQ takes its snapshot of **globalTS**, then regardless of how RQ proceeds it will not include k because the bundle entries finalized by INS do not satisfy t_{RQ} , and thus will not be traversed using **GetNextFromBundle**.
2. There is a node with key equal to k in the data structure when the range query is invoked, and either:
 - (a) No remove operation on k is executed concurrently with RQ. In this case, RQ will include k in its snapshot using **GetNextFromBundle** to collect the result set.
 - (b) A remove(k) operation REM is executed concurrently with RQ. Again, two situations arise:
 - i. REM is linearized before RQ. If REM increments **globalTS** before RQ takes the snapshot of **globalTS**, this implies that REM also installs the necessary pending Bundle entries before RQ takes the snapshot, which means that RQ will have to block until REM finishes, and thus RQ will not include k .
 - ii. REM is linearized after RQ. If REM increments **globalTS** after RQ takes the snapshot of **globalTS**, then regardless of how RQ proceeds it will include k because the bundle entries finalized by REM have a larger timestamp, and thus k is still reachable using **GetNextFromBundle**.
3. Any more complex execution that includes multiple concurrent update operations on k can be easily reduced to one of the above executions since those update operations are conflicting and will block each other using the pending bundle entries.

□

Next, we prove the linearizability of bundled data structures with restartable range queries. The only difference in restartable range queries is that the **pre-range** phase does not use bundles. However, we claim that correctness is still preserved.

Lemma 3. *The **enter-snapshot** step of a restartable range query either returns a node that was in the data structure at its linearization point or restarts the range query.*

Proof. Consider a range query RQ, linearized at t_{RQ} , and whose **pre-range** phase returns **pred** (which is the node reached using **getNext** and used in line 10 of Algorithm 3). We have the following possibilities:

1. **pred** is in the data structure at t_{RQ} . Therefore, based on Lemma 1, entering the snapshot (i.e., calling **GetNextFromBundle** on **pred**) returns a node also in the data structure at t_{RQ} . Accordingly, this case then reduces to the non-restartable case (as if it traversed from the root with **GetNextFromBundle**).
2. **pred** was not in the data structure at t_{RQ} . This may be for two reasons:

- (a) A concurrent thread deleting `pred` is linearized before t_{RQ} but has not yet finalized the deletion. It is still safe to enter the snapshot using `pred` (i.e., call `GetNextFromBundle` on `pred`) since all nodes in RQ’s range that were in the data structure at t_{RQ} are still reachable from `pred`. And, any newly inserted nodes that were not in the data structure at t_{RQ} will not be reachable from `pred` since their timestamps are greater than t_{RQ} .
- (b) A concurrent thread inserting `pred` is linearized after RQ and finalized its bundles before RQ’s pre-range traversal reaches `pred`. In this case RQ will restart because no bundle entry satisfying RQ’s linearization timestamp exists in `pred`.

□

Theorem 2. *Bundled data structures with restartable range queries are linearizable.*

Proof. The linearizability of update operations is the same as the non-restartable case. For range queries, all nodes traversed during the pre-range phase have no impact on correctness because they do not belong in the range. Using Lemma 3, we assert that the range query eventually reaches a node that was in the data structure at t_{RQ} . Once there, the proof for Theorem 1 can be applied to demonstrate the linearizability of restartable range queries. □

Last, we give a definition of our minimality property and a proof for range queries on bundled data structures. To simplify our discussion, we will limit it to non-restartable range queries but informally highlight how to extend it to restartable range queries.

Definition 4. A range query is *minimal* if it only visits nodes that exist in the data structure at its linearization point.

Theorem 3. *Non-restartable range queries in a bundled data structure are minimal.*

Proof. An inductive proof suffices for this theorem. Assume that a non-restartable range query RQ is linearized at t_{RQ} . For the base case, we use Lemma 2 to assert that the first node traversed to by RQ is in the data structure at t_{RQ} . The inductive case follows directly from the `GetNextFromBundle` procedure, RQ only traverses to other nodes also in the data structure at t_{RQ} . Therefore, because RQ only visits nodes in the data structure at t_{RQ} , it is minimal. □

The question of minimality of restartable range queries is more subtle. According to the above definition, restartable range queries in bundled data structures are not minimal since a range query may traverse nodes not in the data structure at its linearization point during the `pre-range` phase. However, we argue that after its `enter-snapshot` step, the traversal is minimal since it can be reduced to the non-restartable case.

To further illustrate this property, consider a non-minimal example. Namely, EBR-RQ as proposed by Arbel-Raviv and Brown. In this strategy, it is possible that a range query visits nodes both during traversal and in the limbo-list that are not in the data structure at the range query’s linearization point. When concurrent updates are numerous, a range query may visit hundreds of such nodes even when ranges are small.